

IMPROVING THE CIVIC POSITION OF FUTURE POLITICAL SCIENTISTS BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract: Interdisciplinarity refers to the study of each discipline as an integrated system based on the similarities between the researched issues and events, while the integrative approach is the integration of fragments or parts of things and events, means that it becomes a whole. The article talks about ways to improve the citizenship position of future political scientists based on an integrative approach.

Key words: integrative approach, civic position, value, thinking, innovative development, strategy, aesthetic culture.

A systemic approach, systemic means a whole thing or event made up of parts. Interdisciplinarity refers to the study of each discipline as an integrated system based on the similarities between the researched issues and events, while the integrative approach is the integration of fragments or parts of things and events, means that it becomes a whole. Both pedagogical concepts create similar, close, complementary, reinforcing ideas and thoughts of the information in the content of the sciences in the process of education and raise the content of the acquired knowledge and increase the intellectual potential of the learner. , enriches the worldview and helps to develop personal qualities in a positive direction. The analysis of literature on pedagogy, didactics, methodology, philosophy, psychology, as a predecessor of interactive education, interdisciplinary education in the 20-30s of the 20th century (V.Y. Yesipov), in the 60-70s, interdisciplinary communication (I.D. Zverev, V.N. Maksimova) , L.V. Tefasov, E.A. Turdikulov), and in the 80s and 90s showed that the issues of integrating the educational process (Y.M. Kolgin, L.V. Tarasov, R.G. Safarova, O.A. Abduquddusov, etc.) were implemented.

Interdisciplinarity, which has replaced interdisciplinarity in the educational system, aims to create the integration of science and educational practice, to deepen and expand knowledge through the scientific expression of information in the content of disciplines that are closely related to each other in terms of content and essence. brought It laid the foundation for the creation of new sciences on the production of time and its operation technology, and served as a

didactic basis for ensuring the effectiveness of the implementation of promising problems. "Interdisciplinarity - writes the well-known Russian pedagogue V.M. Maksimova - as a modern didactic paradigm made it possible to solve complex (holistic) educational problems in the content of sciences, generalize and draw a whole conclusion. At the same time, he activated the methods and methods of education and ensured the systematization of knowledge, skills, and qualifications in the content of various educational subjects. He established a systematic analysis, connected the composition, structure and tasks of interdisciplinarity with various objects, realized the connection between the academic subject and the teaching process therefore, it is a modern didactic principle" [3,30].

Uzbek pedagogue A.Choriyev, while researching the problem of "The importance of interdisciplinary communication in the personnel training system", writes about interdisciplinary communication: "...interdisciplinary communication increases the effectiveness of education, complements one or two, avoids unnecessary repetitions. It does not put. Therefore, it is vital to follow the rule of interdisciplinary communication in the preparation of educational standards, textbooks and training manuals" [4,348]. The author emphasizes that all sciences are close to each other in studying the laws of nature, society, and thought, and this closeness complements the relationship and ensures the effectiveness of education on this basis. "Interdisciplinarity", - writes B.Abdullayeva, - is not only a means of achieving comprehensive development of the student's personality based on general social goals in learning subjects, but also one of the important factors in the formation of specific pedagogical tasks, defining science systems based on knowledge, skills, attitudes" [2,42].

The advantage of integrative teaching of socio-humanitarian and specialized subjects is that they provide opportunities for humanization, democratization, and socialization of the educational process. These opportunities create a favorable pedagogical environment for the development of civic consciousness, civic faith, civic thinking, civic perception and attitudes, which form the basis of civic culture in students. In this sense, based on the requirements of the newly adopted Law "On Education", in order to ensure the integrity of education and develop civic culture among students, the integration of social-humanities and specialized sciences is organized in the following directions We considered it appropriate to:

- science, art, human labor activity, national ideology, philosophy, religion important for socio-economic development and spiritual-enlightenment life with the help of organization of integration of socio-humanitarian and specialized sciences to create a complex of axiological (doctrine of values) knowledge that forms the basis of such valuable values;

- epistemological information about reality, socio-political life, economic-ideological development based on the integrated integration of sciences, important skills for evaluating the practical and educational educational process (proving the superiority of national independence over all systems creation and improvement of justification, humanitarianism of science and technology, threats to man, foreignness of ideologies, ignorance, etc.;

- on the basis of generalized knowledge and skills in the content of socio-humanitarian and specialized sciences, a person's ideological-ideological belief, scientific outlook, moral-aesthetic ideal, spiritual-physical potential, social-economic life and legal-ethical aspects of labor activity on the basis of achieving the composition of the components of civil culture.

Based on these approaches, the organized pedagogical process was designed based on the principles of goal orientation, activity and consciousness, subjectivity and stimulation of activity, humanitarian orientation, succession and collectivity. After all, these principles represent the laws of the educational process, that is, the rules to be followed in studying and teaching. That is why they are an important scientific basis of modern pedagogy.

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